

THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON

Tashmuratov Farrux Yerixonovich

Teacher, Termez state university

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Abstract. Badminton is a recreational and competitive game played in singles (two opposing players) and doubles (two opposing pairs) formats. The aim of the game is to win points by hitting a shuttlecock across the net and into your opponent's court forcing your opponent to make an error and be unable to return the shuttlecock back. The lightness of the racket and the shape of the shuttlecock mean that it is a very fast game requiring good reactions and speed around the court.

Key word: sport, badminton, light, creative, single

In all competitive games of badminton, a net splits the court in half and each individual or pair defends their selected area of the court. To successfully play a game, the following must occur:

- players must serve the shuttlecock over the net so that it lands on the correct side of the opponent's court
- once the serve has crossed the net (without hitting the net), the opposition must select the most appropriate shot to return the shuttlecock to either win the point or gain a tactical advantage
- to win a point, an individual must play a shot that allows the shuttlecock to either hit the floor of their opponent's court or force their opposition to either not return the shuttlecock or land it out of bounds

In badminton, points are scored regardless of who is serving.

History

The beginnings of badminton can be traced to the mid-1800s, where it was created by British military officers stationed in British India. Originally called 'battledore' rather than badminton, its use of a shuttlecock, rather than a ball, has remained constant over the years.

Like most of the racket sports, badminton in England was played by the upper classes. However, rather than the athletic game we see today, it was a simple rally competition where players would try to hit the shuttlecock as many times as possible without it hitting the ground.

The sport of badminton underwent its first significant change in the 1800s when British army officers in India introduced a net and court. The game was brought back to England by retired officers and played at the Duke of Beaufort's home, Badminton House in Gloucestershire. From that point onwards the game became known as badminton.

Playing area

- A competitive badminton court is a large rectangle marked out with 40 mm wide lines. The dimensions of the court are of 13.4 m (44 ft) long and 6.1m (20 ft) wide.
- The badminton posts are 1.55 m (5ft 1 in) in height and must remain perfectly vertical when attached to the strained net. To ensure visibility and safety, the 6.1 m wide net is made from fine dark cord with a mesh of between 15-20 mm.

Players

A badminton match can have either two or four players on the court at a given time.

In a game of doubles, after a service is returned, both players are then able to hit the shuttlecock and are not required to take it in turns.

Competitive badminton games have five different types of matches/events. They are:

1. men's singles
2. women's singles
3. men's doubles
4. women's doubles
5. mixed doubles (each team is made up of a man and a woman)

However, recreational games see women playing against men in singles matches. Wheelchair formats are also offered in all types of competitive badminton matches.

Badminton scoring, rules and officials

Scoring

In recent years, badminton has changed how players can score a point. In 2006, the rules were changed to a rally point system and this now allows both players to score a point during a rally, regardless of who served.

In competitive adult matches, all games are played to a best of three games. To win a game, a player must reach 21 points. However, if the game is tied at 20-20 (or 20-all) then you are required to win by two clear points. Unlike most sports, however, if the score becomes 29-29 (or 29-all), the player or team to score the 30th point will win the game.

Rules

- A match consists of the best of three games of 21 points.
- The player/pair winning a rally adds a point to its score.
- At 20-all, the player/pair which first gains a 2-point lead wins that game.

- At 29-all, the side scoring the 30th point wins that game.
- The player/pair winning a game serves first in the next game.
- A badminton match can be played by two opposing players (singles) or four opposing players (doubles).
- A competitive match must be played indoors utilising the official court dimensions.
- A point is scored when the shuttlecock lands inside the opponent's court or if a returned shuttlecock hits the net or lands outside of the court the player will lose the point.
- At the start of the rally, the server and receiver stand in diagonally opposite service courts.
- A legal serve must be hit diagonally over the net and across the court.
- A badminton serve must be hit underarm and below the server's waist height. The whole of the shuttle should be below 1.15 metres from the surface of the court when it is hit by the server, with the racquet shaft pointing downwards. The shuttlecock is not allowed to bounce. After a point is won, the players will move to the opposite serving stations for the next point.
- The rules do not allow second serves.
- During a point a player can return the shuttlecock from inside and outside of the court.
- A player is not able to touch the net with any part of their body or racket.
- A player must not deliberately distract their opponent.
- A player is not able to hit the shuttlecock twice.
- A 'let' may be called by the referee if an unforeseen or accidental issue arises.
- A game must include two rest periods. These are a 90-second rest after the first game and a 5-minute rest after the second game.

Officials

The referee is in overall charge of a badminton tournament or championship(s) of which a match forms part, to uphold the Laws of Badminton and Competition Regulations in the BWF Statutes.

Individual singles matches require a total of six officials:

- an umpire who is in charge of the match, the court and its immediate surroundings
- four line judges (two for each side of the court positioned at the baseline) who indicate whether a shuttlecock landed 'in' or 'out' on the line(s) assigned
- a service judge

Doubles matches require a total of eight officials. This is as above but an additional two line judges are sometimes added (one for each side of the court positioned at the doubles service line)

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